

A STUDY OF ERRORS MADE BY UAC UNDERGRADUATES IN THE ASSIGNMENT OF STRESS TO WORDS INCLUDING STRESS ATTRACTORS ENDINGS

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ABSTRACT

Among the suprasegmental features of English pronunciation, stress is the most important but it is challenging for EFL and ESL learners. At word level, it is known as lexical stress and it makes some syllables within words be pronounced with more force or energy. Despite being challenging for EFL learners especially, word stress can be mastered with less difficulty when some rules related to words endings and suffixes are known. Some of these endings attract the stress to themselves and are referred to as stress attractors endings. This paper aims at carrying out an investigation of the pronunciation by UAC undergraduates of words including these endings. Data collection for this purpose was carried out through a recorded pronunciation test during which the participants were asked to read freely and in a natural way a list of words which all include these endings. The stress errors made by the participants were separately identified by two faithful and experienced specialists of English phonetics and phonology. Those errors were classified in two categories depending on whether the endings are from French origin or not. Thirty-five at least of fifty-two words with endings not from French origin (67.31%-) were assigned the stress to the wrong syllables by 9 participants (64.29%). As for the endings from French origin, 64.29% of the undergraduates stressed the wrong syllables in at least thirty-nine (73.58% -) of fifty-three words. In this category, there were 7 words which are exceptions to the rule and fewer lexical stress errors were made in their pronunciation by the participants. The same goes for the ten exceptions related to endings not from French origin. These results show that although French the second language of the undergraduates generally has its words stressed on their last syllables, the participants are not used to stressing English words on their last

syllables. Moreover, the results show that the participants not only ignore stress rules related to stress attractors endings. Finally, they were wrongly influenced by the fact that the majority of English words tend to be stressed on syllables closer to their beginnings.

Key words: word stress, syllable, ending, suffix, stress attractor ending, stress rules

RESUME

Parmi les caractéristiques suprasegmentales de la prononciation de l'Anglais, l'accentuation est la plus importante, mais elle constitue un challenge pour les apprenants de l'Anglais comme langue étrangère ou comme seconde langue. Au niveau du mot, l'accentuation consiste à prononcer certaines syllabes d'un mot avec plus de force ou d'énergie. Malgré les difficultés qu'elle pose, en particulier pour les apprenants de l'Anglais comme langue étrangère, l'accentuation des mots peut être maîtrisée plus facilement lorsque certaines règles liées aux terminaisons et aux suffixes sont connues. Certaines de ces terminaisons ou suffixes portent elles-mêmes l'accent. Le présent travail vise à étudier la prononciation, par des étudiants de troisième année de l'UAC, de mots comportant ces terminaisons. Pour ce faire, la collecte de données a consisté en un test de prononciation enregistré au cours duquel il a été demandé aux participants de lire librement et de façon naturelle une liste de mots comportant tous ces terminaisons. Les erreurs d'accentuation commises par les participants ont été identifiées séparément par deux spécialistes expérimentés et rigoureux de la phonétique et de la phonologie de l'Anglais. Ces erreurs ont été classées en deux catégories selon que les terminaisons sont d'origine française ou non. 9 des quatorze participants (64,29 %) ont accentué des syllabes incorrectes pour au moins trente-cinq des cinquante-deux mots comportant des terminaisons qui ne sont pas d'origine française (67,31 %). En ce qui concerne les terminaisons d'origine française, 64,29 % des étudiants ont placé l'accent sur des syllabes incorrectes dans au moins trente-neuf des cinquante-trois mots (73,58 %). Dans cette catégorie, il y avait 7 mots constituant des exceptions à la règle, et moins d'erreurs ont été commises dans leur prononciation par les participants. Il en va de même pour les dix exceptions concernant les mots aux terminaisons qui ne sont pas d'origine française.

Ces résultats montrent que, bien que le Français, deuxième langue des étudiants, ait généralement ses mots accentués sur la dernière syllabe, les participants ne sont pas habitués à accentuer les mots anglais sur leur dernière syllabe. De plus, les résultats révèlent que les participants ignorent non seulement les règles d'accentuation liées aux terminaisons qui portent

l'accent elles-mêmes, mais qu'ils ont également été influencés à tort par le fait que la majorité des mots anglais tendent à être accentués sur des syllabes proches du début du mot.

Mots clés: accentuation de mot, syllabe, terminaison, suffixe, porter l'accent, règles d'accentuation

1. Introduction

English being known as a stress-based language, the position of stress in an English word of more than one syllable is variable. In the words *intelligent*, *application*, and *questionnaire* for example, the stress falls respectively on the antepenultimate syllable, the penultimate syllable and the ultimate or last syllable. This variability shows that emphasis must not be put on a given syllable in an English word at random. This makes it difficult for non-native speakers to stress syllables within words appropriately while speaking English. This is the case of the undergraduates in the English department at the University of Abomey-Calavi (UAC). They have difficulty to assign the stress to the right syllable within words some of which have endings which are referred to as stress attractors endings. Most of those endings are from French origin. We could think that this would have made the pronunciation of words including those endings easier for the undergraduates of the University of Abomey-Calavi who have French as their second language. Unfortunately, this is not often the case as many of those undergraduates do not assign the stress to the right syllable within those words.

The assignment of stress in words which include stress attractors endings is indeed the focus of this research work which first aims at identifying and categorising stress errors made by the UAC undergraduates while pronouncing English words including stress attractors endings. Secondly, rules as well as their exceptions will be stated in order to help non-native speakers in general to assign the stress to the right syllable within those words. Some recommendations will also be made to the UAC undergraduates and EFL learners in general so that they improve their overall pronunciation of English words by assigning the stress to the right syllables.

The findings expected from it will make UAC undergraduates realise that, while speaking English, they do not care enough about the stress pattern of words. Moreover, the stress rules that will be stated will help the undergraduates to stress the words which include stress attractors endings correctly. It is worth mentioning also that the findings expected from the study will lay the ground for further research.

The focus of this research work being the assignment of stress to syllables in words which include stress attractors endings, dealing with words which include other categories of endings will be beyond the scope of the study. This restriction then raises the question of the importance of the words which include for example endings making the stress occur on the syllable just before them. On the other hand, given the holidays period during which the study has been conducted, it has been possible to interview and submit the pronunciation test to only a few number of undergraduates. This gives rise to the generalisation of the findings with those undergraduates to all the undergraduates in the English department at the University of Abomey-Calavi, hence a limitation to the study. Another restriction is related to the fact that the undergraduates who took part in the study were asked to read the words including those endings in isolation. Their pronunciation of those words in isolation might be different from the way they pronounce them in connected speech while reading a text for instance or most importantly while speaking.

In line with the purposes of this study, the following research questions have been answered in this research paper:

- What are the different categories of stress errors made by the UAC undergraduates in the pronunciation of words which include stress attractors endings?
- What rules can help EFL learners in general to assign the stress to the right syllables in words which include stress attractors endings?

2. Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

This chapter forms the theoretical background of this study. It deals with on the one hand, some key concepts (word stress, ending, suffix and root) to this study. On the other hand, writings about these concepts are discussed and stress rules are stated for words which include stress attractors endings.

1.1 Concepts of stress, ending and suffix

1.1.1 Word stress

The process of learning English pronunciation entails the mastery of individual sounds referred to as phonemes, the emphasis put on one or more syllables within words which is known as word stress, sentence stress related to the emphasis on some words within sentences, and intonation patterns which deal with pitch variations and aspects of connected speech (Rasul,

2025: 4). Among these features, word stress is known to play a significant role for any learner of the language willing to achieve successful communication with other speakers of the language. Taseer and Chaudhry (2026: 245) refer to mastering word stress for ESL and EFL learners as “one of the most challenging aspects of pronunciation”. Word stress is an essential component of the pronunciation of the language and is used to communicate clearly. Kunova & Kralova (2025) described it as being not only “an integral and crucial part of English pronunciation” (191) but also as “a decisive factor in communicative clarity” (194). The words “photograph” and “photographer” are for instance distinguishable according to stress placements (Roach, 2002). To stress words appropriately, knowing about some key words related to word formation is important.

1.1.2 Ending, Suffix, Root

Unlike French and many other languages where word stress is predictable, is usually stressed, identifying the syllable to be stressed within English words is challenging for ESL and EFL learners. However, the good news is that endings and suffixes are quite helpful to know which syllable should be stressed within words. Therefore, it is important to know clearly what an ending and a suffix refer to. An ending is “the last part of a word, that is added to a main part” (Oxford, 2005: 482). As for the suffix, Oxford (ibid: 1478) defines it as “a letter or group of letters added to the end of a word to make another word”. Consequently, a suffix may be considered an ending but an ending may not be a suffix as an ending is not supposed to be always added to the end of an already existing word. An ending may then be part of the root of a word whereas a suffix cannot. A root according to Thakur, 2006: 8 is “that part of a word which remains after all the affixes have been removed”, affixes being prefixes or suffixes.

1.2 Overview of relevant writings about stress

In principle, stress alone could serve to distinguish words, but in reality, it seldom does. In English, minimal pairs such as billow/below are distinguished by word stress but they are rare. However, there is evidence to indicate that intelligibility and comprehensibility are undermined specifically by faulty word stress (Cutler & Clifton, 1984; Gallego, 1990; Bond, 1999, Field, 2005). Stressing words the wrong way within phrases or sentences may affect comprehension more adversely than segmental errors do. Rasul (2025: 11) stated that when native speakers come across unfamiliar words, they can pronounce them with the right stress pattern. According to Cooper et al, 2002; Sanders, Neville, & Woldorff, 2002; Slowiaczek, 1990, native speakers of

English rely on word stress to recognise isolated words. As the importance of the right placement of stress is known, more attention has to be given to its teaching in English phonetics and phonology classes in particular. This will help the undergraduates of the University of Abomey-Calavi and other EFL learners to avoid stress-related errors while speaking. They will for example avoid pronouncing the noun desert /'dezət/ (dry place) as the noun desert /dɪ'zɜ:t/ (something deserved). By avoiding those errors, they will make themselves understood correctly while speaking. But, is word stress the easiest aspect of pronunciation to teach in a phonetics class?

Word stress causes problems to the undergraduates of the University of Abomey-Calavi and other learners of English as a foreign language. Effective word stress teaching should therefore play a non-negligible role in learners' instruction even if rules related to it reveal themselves as being complex. Rasul (2025: 24) described rules and patterns associated with English stress as intricate, which makes it difficult for EFL learners to correctly utilise stress in spoken English. Varied approaches are then used to teach them. Avery and Ehrlich (1992) argued that there are no hard and fast rules for English word stress and that stress patterns should be learnt at the same time as new vocabulary, but they still provide a few general rules about word stress based on suffixes and endings. Those rules apply to many categories of words considering their endings. Among those words, there are words which are mainly from French origin and include endings which are said to be stress attractors endings as they carry the stress themselves. How have data been collected for the purpose of this study?

3. Research methodology

For the purpose of this research work, the qualitative and quantitative methods were used. The qualitative method lays emphasis on the interpretation of qualitative data from a variety of sources whereas the quantitative method entails the presentation of data in statistical form (Newman 1997). Both methods involve collecting and analysing data.

2.1 Data collection

To collect data for this study, secondary data sources were used. Those data were data from books and articles consulted on internet and books read at "American Corner" located in "Maison des Jeunes de Porto-Novo". The rationale for using these documents was to get more information about the assignment of stress to English words in general. Specifically, using these

documents help to have a great number of words which include stress attractors endings in order to use them for the pronunciation test with the participants who were fourteen undergraduates from the University of Abomey-Calavi whom we managed to contact with the help of the prefects. This has not been easy as they were on holidays.

The objective underlying the pronunciation test was to be aware of mainly the stress errors they make in the pronunciation of words which include stress attractors' endings.

2.2 Data analysis

Using Newman's (1997) qualitative and quantitative approach, the data elicited from books, the pronunciation test were categorised based on the information extracted and then analysed. Statistics in tabular form was used specifically for the data drawn from the pronunciation test.

3. Findings and discussions

3.1 Findings

This part of the study deals with the presentation of wrongly stressed English words which include stress attractors endings. Those words have been classified in two categories. The first category is made up of words which are not from French origin and have the endings *-ain*, *-ee*, *-eer*, *-oo*, *-oon*, *-self*, *-selves*... The second category includes words which are from French origin, most of them being directly French borrowings. Those words end in *-ade*, *-aire*, *-eur*, *-euse*, *-ique*, *-esque*, *-V(s)que*, *-elle*, *-ette*.

As far as the first category is concerned, the pronunciation test includes fifty-two of those words. 9 (64.29%) of the fourteen undergraduates put the main stress on the wrong syllable in at least 35 (67.31%) of the words. Apart from those fifty-two words, ten words from the same category of endings function as exceptions to the rule of stress assignment to the last syllable. As for these ten words (*coffee* / 'kɒfi /, *toffee* / 'tɒfi /, *pedigree* / 'pedɪgri: /, *cuckoo* / 'kʊku: /, *reindeer* / 'reɪndɪə/, *igloo* / 'ɪglu: /, *mongoose* / 'mʌŋgu:s /, *bugaboo* / 'bʌgəbu: /, *yankee* / 'jæŋki /, *trochee* / 'trəʊki: /), at most 3 (30%) of them were assigned the stress to the wrong syllable by eleven undergraduates. The other 3 undergraduates assigned the stress to the wrong syllable in 4-6 words. We can conclude that most of the undergraduates are accustomed to assigning the stress to the syllable(s) before the final syllable while pronouncing the words from this first category of endings. (Table 1)

Number of words	Percentage (%)	Examples of words	Number of undergraduates	Percentage (%)	Phonemic transcription of the errors (wrong stressed syllables in bold)
35	67.31	Chinese trainee taboo saloon	9	64.29	/ 'tʃaɪni:z / / 'treɪni: / / 'təbu: / / 'səlu:n /
1-3	10-30	(Exceptions) pedigree jubilee toffee	11	78.57	/ peɪdɪ'ɡri: / / dʒu:bi'li: / / tɒ'fi /
4-6	40-60	(Exceptions) toffee reindeer bugaboo	3	21.43	/ tɒ'fi / / re'ɪndɪə / / bʌ'gəbu: /

Table 1: Main stress assignment to the wrong syllable in words which have the main stress on their final syllable and are not from French origin

The category of endings which are from French origin includes sixty words. Among those sixty words, 7 are exceptions to the rule, that is, fifty-three words respect the rule. 39 (73.58%) at least of those fifty-three words were wrongly assigned the stress, that is, they were assigned the stress to any of their syllables but the last, by 9 of the undergraduates. 5 undergraduates pronounced the words the way they are pronounced in French. As for the 7 exceptions (*renegade* / 'renɪgeɪd /, *marmalade* / 'mɑ:məleɪd /, *grandeur* / 'grændʒə /, *etiquette* / 'etɪket /, *netiquette* / 'netɪket /, *omelet or omelette* / 'ɒmlət /, *vaudeville* / 'vɔ:dəvɪl /), two (2) or three (3) of them were assigned the stress to the wrong syllable by the undergraduates. The words on which the stress was wrongly assigned include *marmalade*, *etiquette* and *netiquette*. (Table 2)

Number of words	Percentage (%)	Examples of words	Number of undergraduates	Percentage (%)	Phonemic transcription of the errors (wrong stressed syllables in bold)
39	73.58	kitchenette picturesque lemonade	9	64.29	/ 'kɪʃɪnet / / 'pɪktʃəresk / / le'məneɪd /
2-3 (7 exceptions)	28.57-42.86	marmalade etiquette	14	100	/ mɑ:mə'leɪd / / etɪ'ket /

Table 2: Main stress assignment to the wrong syllable in words from French origin which have the main stress on their final syllable

3.2 Discussions

This section of the study is concerned with the discussion of the stressing of English words including stress attractors endings by the UAC undergraduates learning English as a foreign language.

To begin with, words like *trainee*, *marquee*, *banshee*, *cockatoo*, *balloon*, *saloon*, *trustee*, *canteen*, *dragoon*, *tycoon*, *typhoon*, *cartoon*, *referee*, *volunteer*, *guarantee*, *detainee*, *pharisee*, *devotee*, *addressee*, *engineer*, *dedicatee*, *refugee*, *pioneer*, *garnishee*, *Maltese*, *Burmese*, *Chinese*, *Beninese*, *Portuguese*, *Togolese*, *pentagonese*, *Vietnamese*, *myself*, *itself*, *herself*, *yourselves*, *themselves*, *nominee*, *vaccinee* which are normally stressed on their last syllable, are wrongly stressed either on their penultimate syllable or even sometimes on their antepenultimate syllable when they are made up of more than two syllables. Contrary to these words which are normally stressed on their last syllable, there are some words with an ending from the same group which are wrongly stressed when their last syllable is given prominence. They are among the exceptions to the rule. These words are: *pedigree*, *jubilee*, *bugaboo*, which are stressed on their antepenultimate syllable and *cuckoo* normally stressed on its penultimate syllable. Let us note that the word *bugaboo* is also wrongly assigned the main stress on its penultimate syllable.

- The words *banquette*, *roulette*, *galette*, *cassette*, *gazelle*, *quenelle*, *noblesse*, *aquarelle*, *bizarre*, *bagatelle*, *giraffe*, *tristesse*, *finesse*, *parade*, *brigade*, *unique*, *antique*, *technique*, *grotesque*, *burlesque*, *romanesque*, *picturesque*, *liqueur*, *danseur*, *voyeur*, *masseuse*, *connoisseur*, *solitaire*, *questionnaire*, *billionaire*, *silhouette*, *kitchenette*, *marquise*, *majorette*, *bassinette*, *clarinet*, *bayonet* whose main stress falls on the last syllable are stressed

either on their penultimate or antepenultimate syllable. Functioning as exceptions to the rule, the words *renegade* and *marmalade* are wrongly stressed when their last syllable is given prominence as it was the case by some undergraduates. The word *marmalade* was also wrongly stressed on their penultimate syllable. Those two words which function as exceptions to the rule have a /100/ stress pattern. The endings of this category of words being from French origin, almost all those words are borrowed from French. Therefore, some undergraduates even pronounce them the way they are pronounced in French.

The feature of paramount importance any learner of English as a foreign language has to know is “*stress*”, English being referred to as a stress-based language. Some syllables within words are then said with more prominence than others. In Benin, the official language is French, a syllable-timed language. This makes the feature of stress in English difficult for Beninese English learners to master. Stress is the most important suprasegmental feature which is the basis for the other features of suprasegmental phonetics. Unfortunately, this very important feature is not given the importance it deserves in the teaching of the English language. Therefore, in order to avoid so many stress-related errors by the great majority of English department undergraduates while speaking the language, stress which has a great importance in achieving intelligibility has to be given the importance it deserves.

4. Conclusion

All in all, this research paper shows that the English department undergraduates don’t really know the extent to which stress is important in the English language. Those among them who care about the language good speaking just try as much as they can to pronounce the words with the correct vowel and consonant sounds. By doing so, the consequence is that they stress words inappropriately.

In this study, we identified those stress errors by undergraduates in the English department of the University of Abomey-Clavi in the case of words which include stress attractors endings. The errors the undergraduates make concerning this category of words can be explained on the one hand by the fact that, knowing stress rules or not, they are not used to stressing English words of more than two syllables especially on their last syllable. As a matter of fact, English doesn’t include many words of more than two syllables mainly which are stressed on their last syllable. On the other hand, many of the words including stress attractors endings being from French origin and French being the second language of the undergraduates, some of

them surely find it abnormal to stress those words on their last syllable as they sound French in a certain way, even though some others pronounce them exactly the way they are pronounced in French.

To help the English department undergraduates achieve intelligibility and comprehensibility, great focus has to be made on stress in EFL teaching.

4. Recommendations

Hoping this study will play an important role in helping EFL learners to avoid some stress-related errors, we don't ignore that there are many other endings which have an influence on the stress pattern of English words. Therefore, based on the main findings and limitations of this study, below are some recommendations for further research and some stress rules related to stress attractors endings.

- Neutral endings and other categories of strong endings must also be considered in order for EFL learners in general to avoid many more stress-related errors while speaking the language;
- More undergraduates should be involved in the study of stress-related errors in English;
- EFL learners in general should bear in mind that knowing how a word is stressed is essential when they use it themselves for the first time because even if their production of the speech sounds is accurate, they will often be misunderstood if they place the stress on the wrong syllable;
- Not only EFL learners but also ESL learners should know about the rules below about words including stress attractors endings in order to avoid word stress errors within this category of words.

Stress rules for words including stress attractors' endings

In English, stress attractors endings which in majority are from French origin and bear the stress themselves are:

- -ade, -aire, -ese, -esce, -eur, -euse, -ain (verbs)
- -ique, -esque: -V(s)que
- -elle, -ette
- -ee, -een, -eer, -oo, -oon, -self, -selves
- -itis, -osis, -C oma

Some examples are:

➤ -ade

Parade / pə'reɪd /

Brigade / brɪ'geɪd /

Barricade / bæ'rɪ'keɪd /

Lemonade / ,lemə'neɪd /

Dissuade / drɪ'sweɪd /

Persuade / pə'sweɪd /

Accolade / 'ækələɪd / or / ,ækə'leɪd / Decade (ten years) / 'dekeɪd / or / dek'eɪd / or / drɪ'keɪd /

Exceptions: Renegade / 'renɪgeɪd / Marmalade / 'mɑ:mələɪd / Decade (division of the rosary) / 'dekəd /

➤ -ain (verbs)

Maintain / meɪn'teɪn /

Obtain / əb'teɪn /

Entertain / ,entə'teɪn /

➤ -aire

Questionnaire / ,kwɛstʃə'neə /

Billionaire / ,bɪljə'neə /

➤ -ese, -esce, -eur, -euse, -self, -selves

Chinese / tʃaɪ'ni:z /

Siamese / saɪə'mi:z /

Portuguese / pɔ:tʃə'gi:z /

Manganese / 'mæŋgəni:z / or / ,mæŋgə'ni:z /

Acquiesce / ,æk.wi'es / Convalesce / ,kɒnvə'les / Luminesce / ,lu:.mɪ'nes /

Liqueur / lɪ'kjʊə / Connoisseur / ,kɒnə'sɜ: /

Berceuse / beə'sɜ:z / Masseuse / mə'sɜ:z /

Myself / maɪ'self / Ourselves / ,aʊə'self / Themselves / ðəm'selvz / Yourselves / jɔ:'selvz /

Amateur / 'æmətə / or / ,æm.ə'tɜ: / Chauffeur / 'ʃəʊfə / or / ʃəʊ'fɜ: /

Exception: Grandeur / 'grændʒə /

➤ -ique, -esque: -V(s)que

Unique / ju:'ni:k /

Antique / æn'ti:k /

Technique / tek'ni:k /

Grotesque / grəʊ'tesk / Picturesque / ,pɪktʃə'resk / Romanesque / ,rəʊmə'nesk /

➤ -elle, -ette

Quenelle / kə'nel /

Aquarelle / ,ækwə'rel /

Gazelle / gə'zel /

Kitchenette / kɪtʃɪ'net /

Silhouette / sɪlu:'et /

Roulette / ru:'let /

Let us note that the words “Personnel” / ,pɜ:sən'el /, “Lapel” / lə'pel / and Clarinet / ,klærɪ'net / are stressed as if they had “-elle” and “-ette” as endings respectively.

Exceptions : Etiquette / 'etɪket / Netiquette / 'netɪket /

Omelet or Omelette / 'ɒmlət /

Vaudeville / 'vɔ:dəvɪl /

➤ -ee, -een, -eer, -oo, -oon

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APPENDIX

Pronunciation test

Part I

Read the following words clearly.

1. Trainee, yankee, taboo, bamboo, payee, marquee, papoose, toffee, cuckoo, tattoo, kangaroo, banshee, cockatoo, bugaboo
2. Balloon, saloon, trustee, degree, career, coffee, dragoon, tycoon, canteen, trochee
3. Careen, yahoo, typhoon, thirteen, seventeen, igloo, cartoon, mongoose
4. Referee, guarantee, employee, volunteer, detainee, pharisee

5. Nominee, vaccinee, pedigree, devotee, addressee
6. Dedicatee, engineer, refugee, pioneer, jubilee, garnishee, reindeer
7. Obtain, Burmese, Chinese, Siamese, Beninese, entertain
8. Maltese, Portuguese, maintain, Pentagonese, Togolese, Vietnamese.

Part II

Read the following words clearly.

1. Banquette, roulette, galette, clarinet, bagatelle, vaudeville, kitchenette, marquissette, giraffe, etiquette, cabinet, bizarre, majorette, bassinette, netiquette, tristesse, usherette
2. Gazelle, quenelle, noblesse, aquarelle, cassette, omelette, silhouette, bayonet, finesse
3. Parade, brigade, dissuade, estrade, persuade, decade
4. Renegade, opaque, grotesque, promenade, antique, accolade arabesque, picturesque
5. Unique, barricade, technique, palissade, lemonade, marmalade, burlesque, romanesque, oblique,
6. Liqueur, chauffeur, solitaire, danseur, masseuse
7. Billionaire, grandeur, amateur, voyeur, connoisseur, questionnaire.